

Using Twitter as a community for researcher mental health - a workshop

*Guneri, Fatma - Lille Catholic University
McCashin, Darragh – Dublin City University*

(Underline the track, which suits your abstract the most. You can select more than one track)

1. Scientific and practitioners' research presentations
 - a. Bottom-up and community-driven interventions
 - b. Institutional interventions and policies
 - c. Policy-Level insights
2. Workshop/hands-on practices for enhancing researcher mental health and well-being

Length: 446 words

Background

The deteriorating mental health and wellbeing of researchers has been well documented in both the academic literature and the media. A common thread to the experiences of those suffering within the academic system is a series of toxic cultural practices that often occur in silence. Although there has been much negative coverage about the effects of social media, some platforms –in particular, Twitter – have emerged as a key window into the both positive and negative experiences of researcher mental health stakeholders. A plethora of bottom-up initiatives have utilised Twitter to facilitate themed dialogue on the interaction of academia and mental health, such as @AcademicChatter, @PhdVoice, and @hapy_researchers. Additionally, such accounts strategically apply relevant hashtags to communicate notable themes of interest, especially #AcademicMentalHealth. Despite an abundance of Twitter research in other domains, little research nor practical training regarding the optimal usage of Twitter for researcher mental has yet been formulated.

Workshop objectives

- To critically understand the current science and policy underpinning the use of Twitter to facilitate dialogue on researcher mental health
- To showcase initial findings from a research-in-progress project concerning the themes emerging from specific researcher mental health accounts
- To learn hands-on skills as to how you can engage with Twitter – best practices, ethical guidance and useful tools will be demonstrated, in addition to helpful accounts/hashtags and networks highlighted. A full Q-&-A will be hosted.

- To facilitate discussion on how ReMO can leverage Twitter to further the project mission, and promote further stakeholder engagement.

Workshop content

This workshop will apply a three-part format to empower the ReMO community to achieve the aforementioned objectives.

Part 1 will involve a broad research and policy overview as to how science and policy-makers currently approach the topic of Twitter engagement, with reference to high quality research from other fields. Using ongoing data analysis, initial findings from a research-in-progress project concerning the themes emerging from specific researcher mental health accounts will be presented to stimulate further insights into how the ReMO community is engaging with Twitter.

Part 2 will then transition into a hands-on workshop to empower those wishing to engage with Twitter – best practices, ethical guidance and useful tools will be demonstrated, in addition to helpful accounts/hashtags and networks highlighted. A full Q-&-A will be hosted throughout, as will support for those who are new to the platform.

Part 3 will see a facilitated group discussion occur. A critical reflection on lessons from the preceding parts will be shared. Thereafter, the workshop will brainstorm how these reflections are applicable to the ReMO mission – how can Twitter be a powerful tool in promoting further networking, stakeholder engagement – and crucially – a tool for good in the furthering of mental health dialogue.